

E-Marketing

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Meaning

E-Marketing is also known as Internet Marketing, Web Marketing, Digital Marketing, or Online Marketing. E-marketing is the process of marketing a product or service using the Internet or via e-mail and wireless media. It uses a range of technologies to help connect businesses to their customers. E-mail is referred to those strategies and techniques which utilized online ways to reach target customers. There are million of internet users that daily access different websites using a variety of tools using the computer, laptop, tablets and smart phones and the number of internet users are increasing very rapidly. The internet is the most powerful tool that can put any business on solid footing with market hands. E-marketing continues to offer substantial qualifiable benefits to companies with advanced web system.

Objectives of E-Marketing

Increase Revenue

The primary goal of any marketing strategy is ultimately to increase revenue. The Internet provides plenty of opportunities for every business and with strategies like content marketing and social media marketing, it can position as an expert.

Build a Brand

Well-known brands are typically trusted more by customers. The internet is a great tool for building that trust, as it has a wide reach and allows directly to connect with individuals.

Improve Local SEO

Many small businesses focus much of their marketing efforts on improving their local SEO. This means optimizing various elements on their sites to attract local customers who are looking for the services they provide.

Increase Qualified Traffic

By targeting marketing to specific persons and aiming to attract specific, qualified people, the company can increase the ROI of its marketing efforts.

Manage Online Reputation

It is important for businesses to maintain a solid online reputation. This means monitoring your company's name, maintaining social profiles, and responding to bad reviews accordingly. 2

Become an Influencer

The people who become experts and influencers are those who strategically position themselves to give out great advice and information. Efforts taken by the company can position them as an expert not only in the eyes of other industry professional but also in the eyes of potential clients.

Types of E-Marketing

To maximize business marketing opportunity online, there are different types of e-marketing. Each type of e-marketing requires specialized knowledge, skills and flare to ensure that it is effective.

Search Engine Marketing (SEM)

Search engine marketing is the practice of marketing business using paid advertisements that appear on search engine results pages (or SERPs). Advertisers bid on keywords that users of services such as Google and Bing might enter when looking for certain products or services, which gives the advertiser the opportunity for their ads to appear alongside results for those search queries. Search engine marketing's greatest strength is that it offers advertisers the opportunity to put their ads in front of motivated customers who are ready to buy at the precise moment they are ready to make a purchase.

Search Engine Optimization(SEO)

The way of the SEO is to make website pages rank higher in the search engine result pages to increase visibility, authority and Alexa scores. The higher a page positions, the more striking and unhidden it is, and along these lines will get more activity, traffic, and conversions.

Blogging

Blogging makes to the list of different types of online marketing channels because dealing with that channel is true expertise all alone. Planning content, labeling and ordering content properly, overseeing interior linking, upgrading navigations, these are only a modest bunch of things that a genuine "blogger" oversees.

Content Marketing

Content marketing is the ongoing process that focuses on communicating with customers without always selling. Businesses use content marketing strategies to educate the consumer while delivering consistent, valuable information to buyers who, in turn, reward us with their business and loyalty.

Facebook

Facebook Ad is an advanced tool for creating marketing campaigns targeted to mesmerized, targeted audiences. Facebook allows testing multiple ad formats within a single campaign and multiple ads within a group. All these opportunities make Facebook an ideal place for e-marketing, which can use to build brand awareness, create an audience on the fan page, or generate leads by redirecting traffic to the website. 3

Internet Auctions

Online Auctions are related to the sale of a product through a specific auction platform. Online auctions allow purchasing an item or service over the internet in a simple way. It is worth to use them not only to sell products but also to draw attention to the company or brand. Internet auctions are an important sales channel from which many users begin their buying path. Presenting a product even among competitors in most cases will be a very good strategy. Also, there is the ability to redirect traffic from auctions directly to our website that is also a tool to generate traffic on the site and thereby generate sales and promote the brand through marketing outside the auction.

Pay-Per-Click (PPC)

Pay per click is one of the speediest types of marketing channels to drive targeted traffic to web pages and related services. Advertising which is presented on speculation by a web publisher such as a search engine results page or a home page on a browser which only charges the advertiser for the number of times someone clicks on the ad to go to the targeted web site, not the number of viewers of the advertisement. Pay per click promotions are no longer displayed on the sidebar on search engines, and now they can be shown on niche sites, or they may also act as sponsored stories on different social media networks. PPC ads can be shown as product listing, or as a video ad.

Social Media

Social Media is the youngest and as appealing as innovative and powerful. Many have grasped the utilization of social stages to advance their brand image. Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms and websites to promote a product or service. Most social media platforms have transiting data analytical tool, which enables the company to track the program, success and engagement of ad companies.

Affiliate Marketing

Affiliate marketing is the process of earning a commission by promoting other company's products. "Affiliates" market their products, such as through a web site, but have links to other websites unrelated to their site, but have some interest in common with consumers. Affiliates are rewarded for the number of times someone links from their site to the targeted site. Each affiliate-marketing program has its guidelines, controls, and prerequisites for a dealer to be acknowledged and to stay in the program. Many affiliate marketers will give their one of a kind substance in addition to the affiliate service or product to construct the estimation of the deal.

E-Mail Marketing

E-Mail marketing consists of a text message, a combination of words and images such as in a display ad, or provide access to a video on a web site or public video site such as YouTube. E-mail marketing can offer a link to a specific web site to drive traffic and revenue to that site. E-mail marketing is the act of sending a commercial message, 4

Typically a group of people using e-mail. It usually involves solicit sales and donations and is meant to be in loyalty, trust or brand awareness.

Permission Marketing

The idea behind this type of marketing is that a marketer asks for and receives permission from the customer to send him or her information about the company's products and services. The most common way for a marketer to ask for permission is via forms with "opt-in" and "opt-out" checkboxes. If a customer decides to opt-in, a marketer will send appropriate advertising material

via email and or mail. In contrast, if a customer decides to opt-out, then no advertising will be sent by the marketer. By giving permission, a customer essentially displays trust towards the marketer. To make permission marketing successful, a marketer must not abuse this trust by sending unwanted advertisements to the customer or sell their contact information to other companies.

Viral Marketing

Viral marketing describes any strategy that encourages individuals to pass on a marketing message to others, creating the potential for exponential growth in the message's exposure and influence. Like viruses, such strategies take advantage of rapid multiplication to explode the message to thousands, to millions. In comparison to the traditional marketing, viral marketing equals that of a "word-of-mouth." In the world of the Internet, "the word" is spread mostly via email, meaning that the marketing messages can reach others in a much faster and more efficient way in comparison to "old fashioned" face-to-face communication. Thus, messages can be spread to many more recipients in a shorter time, with virtually no cost to the marketer.

E-Marketing Tactics

Google Ad Words

Google AdWords is a great way to reach customers who are researching products specialty. But without the right keywords, one can research the best keywords to use, then monitor results to determine whether it is necessary to adjust strategy.

Experiential Marketing

Brands are increasingly investing in experiences as a marketing tool. AnyRoad's Experience Relationship Manager (ERM) is built to leverage data from the entire customer journey. With this solution in place, it is possible to measure the impact of experiences, calculate the ROI of experiential marketing.

Facebook Advertising

Facebook advertising may already be a vital part of the strategy, but there are tools that help to get the most out of the platform. One of those tools is Hootsuite, which not only offers a complete guide but also a solution that can test and measure performance. 5

Linkedin Advertising

The key to success with LinkedIn campaigns is on the platform itself. LinkedIn provides features like enhanced ad targeting and the ability to save previous campaigns. It is easier to create and manage ads on the site.

Social Media Marketing

Tools are now available to monitor conversations that are happening on social, but it is also important to know what to do with the information once gathered. Social data can not only improve marketing campaigns, but also the overall business strategy.

Youtube Marketing

Many marketers now use YouTube for their advertising efforts, but growing followers on the site can be challenging. It is important to monitor activity on YouTube channel, as well as comments on posts.

Guest Blogging

Although content on own blog can help boost search rankings, one should also spend time placing content on other sites. The key to successful guest blogging is identifying blogs that can reach customers in own niche. Through the list of desired sites, one can reach out with an offer to write a post.

Localization

Today's tools give marketers the power to target customers specifically based on their current location. Although this type of marketing demands discretion on the part of marketers, when used correctly, it can give us the power to reach out to nearby shoppers with targeted offers.

Reviews

Positive reviews on sites like Yelp can bring a big boost to a business's online reach. But those reviews don't appear overnight. It is important to use solutions that monitor reviews of the brand online to take action as quickly as possible if a customer reports a bad experience.

Email Personalization

Automation can create email campaigns that get results, which can keep customers reading. In addition to personalizing subject lines, emails can also be created that appeal specifically to customer segments.

Website Personalization

Currently, every customer who visits site may see the same landing page. As marketing has evolved, though, brands are segmenting customers and displaying pages that more closely target their needs. For instance, a returning customer may see a page with one information type, while a new customer sees another. 6

Content Customization

Beyond the information on the landing page, the content throughout the site can also be customized. Companies like Netflix and Amazon have turned content customization into an art, displaying products that customers are likely to be interested in based on past activities. This type of marketing will only grow more sophisticated as brands access the tools that make it easy to personalize and segment.

Advantages of E-Marketing

- Global reach
- Lower cost
- Interactive
- Highly personalised
- Faster response
- Simplest
- Targeted marketing
- Measurable results

Disadvantages of E-Marketing

- Lack of personal approach
- Dependability on technology which is changing rapidly

- Constant security and privacy issues
- Worldwide competition through globalization
- Dealing with multicultural markets
- Working under different international legal and policy issue which are in the most cause not harmonised.
- Maintenance cost due to constantly evolving environment.

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